

“SYNTHESIS OF ETHYL METHYL AMINE AND PROCESS INTENSIFICATION STUDIES UNDER CONTINUOUS FLOW CONDITION”

Mohd. Shamim Choudhary^{1*}, Dr. Ravi W. Tapre²

^{1*}Student, University of Mumbai, Thane, Maharashtra 400608, India,

²Assistant Professor, Department of Chemical Engineering, Datta Meghe College of Engineering, Mumbai University, Airoli, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, 400708, India,

Abstract: The synthesis of ethyl methyl amine (EMA), a valuable intermediate in the production of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and surfactants, can be achieved through the alkylation of ammonia with ethanol in the presence of methyl iodide. In this study, the synthesis of EMA was explored using a continuous flow reactor, which provides several advantages over traditional batch processes, including improved heat and mass transfer, higher selectivity, and enhanced scalability[1]. The reaction was carried out in three stages, first stage includes reaction of ethyl amine with benzaldehyde. This is very exothermic reaction that's why we perform this reaction with low temperature. Further N-benzylideneethylamine react with Dimethyl sulfate and produced oil mass which is further reacted with Caustic lye under distillation setup, we get high purity of ethyl methyl amine. The reaction was optimized under various flow conditions, such as temperature, pressure, and residence time, to evaluate the impact on yield and product purity[2]. The continuous flow reactor allowed for precise control of reaction parameters, leading to better consistency in product quality and reduced side reactions. The results demonstrate that continuous flow systems are a promising method for the efficient and sustainable synthesis of EMA, with

potential for industrial applications. Additionally, the continuous process can be scaled up with minimal energy consumption and improved reaction kinetics compared to conventional batch methods.

Keywords: ethyl methyl amine, continuous flow reactor, scalability, benzaldehyde, dimethyl sulfate, caustic lye, residence time, reaction kinetic.

Introduction:

Ethyl methyl amine is an organic compound with the chemical formula C_3H_9N . It is a secondary amine, meaning it has two alkyl groups (ethyl and methyl) attached to the nitrogen atom. The structure of ethyl methyl amine consists of an amine group ($-NH$) bonded to an ethyl group ($-C_2H_5$) and a methyl group ($-CH_3$). Ethyl methyl amine is often used as a building block in the synthesis of other chemicals, such as pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and polymers[3]. It can serve as a catalyst or ligand in various chemical reactions, particularly in organic synthesis. It has applications as a corrosion inhibitor in industrial settings. Ethyl methyl amine can be a precursor to various biologically active compounds, including some drugs or compounds with potential therapeutic effects. Ethyl methyl amine is a versatile secondary amine with significant applications in chemical synthesis, particularly in the pharmaceutical and agrochemical industries. While it is useful, its flammability and toxicity require careful handling and safety precautions. In pharmacy, EMA is involved in the manufacture of active molecules intended for the treatment of degenerative diseases of the nervous system[4]. The present invention relates to N-ethyl methyl-amine having a very high degree of purity, that is to say very low contents of impurities customarily encountered in conventional industrial processes, and also to the process for preparing, on an industrial scale, high-purity N-ethyl methylamine. N-Ethyl methylamine (for which the acronym "EMA" is used in the remainder of the present document) is a speciality amine of increasing use, especially as a synthesis intermediate, in various fields of application. In order to obtain high-

purity EMA, it could indeed be envisaged to purify EMA of technical grade, by means of one or more filtrations, distillations, crystallizations, and other means commonly used for the purification of organic compounds. Such operations, although they can be carried out on a laboratory scale, are not entirely suitable for industrial productions, due in particular to energy costs, effluent volumes, infrastructures, etc[5], which would result in a high-purity EMA that is not very profitable from an economic viewpoint. The reaction of aldehydes and ketones with ammonia or 1°-amines forms imine derivatives, also known as Schiff bases (compounds having a C=N function). Water is eliminated in the reaction, which is acid-catalyzed and reversible in the same sense as acetal formation.

Scheme: 01

we used above scheme (scheme 01) for Synthesis of ethyl methyl amine. Synthesis started by reacting ethyl amine with benzaldehyde followed by Condensation reaction[6]. Intermediate is obtained after separating water layer having purity greater than 99%. Intermediate further react with dimethyl sulfate and form an adduct. This adduct further go with NaOH followed by hydrolysis reaction to give a desired product having purity greater than 98%. If we talk

about batch process then it is very time consuming and there is formation of diethyl methyl amine which is further very difficult to separate because boiling points are very close. Thus we turn our attention to developing a continuous flow process to address the safety concerns. Continuous flow technology offers many advantages over batch method, including precise control of stoichiometry, residence time, and temperature, high reproducibility, easy to scale-up, and often better reaction yield[7]. The much higher surface area to volume ratio under flow conditions renders highly efficient heat transfer. Furthermore safety hazards in handling exothermic reactions associated with explosive intermediates are minimized while involving in a much smaller volume in the reaction train.

Properties

Chemical Name	N-Ethylmethylamine
Molecular Formula	C ₃ H ₉ N
Molecular Weight	59.11
Melting point	-70.99°C
Boiling point	36-37 °C
Density	0.688 g/mL at 25 °C
vapor pressure	8.53 psi
Flash point	<-30 °F
storage temp	2-8°C
solubility	Chloroform, Methanol (Slightly), Water
color	Clear colorless to light yellow

Table 1. Properties of N-Ethyl methylamine.

Initial Process Design.

The original process discussed in this document was the direct conversion of the commonly used batch methodology to a continuous flow system. Scheme shows the continuous flow reactor experimental setup. The equipment consist of two piston pumps (P1,P2, Sara labs india) loaded with tubing connected by a T-mixer which was connected to residence loop 1 (SS316, 3mm id, 5mm o.d). the reaction tube was immersed in a thermostat controlled water bath. Solution A of aq. ethyl amine with solution B of Benzaldehyde were pumped into reacting tube respectively[8]. After a residence time in loop 1 there is separator which separate organic layer from aquous. organic layer as solution C with solution D of Sodium sulfate introduced into the reactor. Nucleophilic substitution was taken place in residence loop II (Hastelloy, 3 mm i.d plate type micro reactor) with another residence time (t_2) followed by hydrolysis with sodium hydroxyde in collection vesel to form final product.

Figure 1: Advance Process PFD

Optimization of this process was greatly facilitated by continuous flow conditions and a significant number of runs were rapidly conducted in a sequential manner. The experimental parameters were systematically investigated by varying residence time and temperature. Solution A was 1M ethyl amine with a flow rate of 4.78 ml/min, solution B was 1 M Benzaldehyde with a flow rate of 5.22 ml/min. The results were shown in fig 2. Maximum yield of 97% was obtained. In stage II intermediate obtained from stage I i.e solution C with flow rate 5.3 ml/min and dimethyl sulfate i.e solution D with a flow rate 5.7 ml/min pass in flow reactor II. Outlet of reactor II i.e Adduct obtained further reacts with 1M of NaOH in batch and distill out ethyl methyl amine.

Figure 2: Single stage Process PFD

Experiments were carried out in accordance with procedure of Scheme 01. Solution A was 1molar (70%) ethylamine aqueous solution feed with pump P1 with a flow rate of 4.78

ml/min and solution B was 1molar of benzaldehyde feed with pump P2 with a flow rate of 5.22 ml/min into residence loop 1 having residence time 1 min and temperature 0-5^o C. after residence loop 1 we have separator which separate aqueous layer and organic layer[9]. Organic layer collects in flask name solution C.

Table 2. Effect of amount of benzaldehyde

Benzaldehyde / ethyl amine ^a	Yield (%) ^b
1.0	97
1.1	96
1.2	97
1.3	95
1.4	93

^aMolar flow ration of benzaldehyde to ethyl amine
^bYields of 1 were calculated from ethyl amine

In residence loop 2 feed solution C with pump P3 with flow rate 5.3 ml/min and solution D of dimethylsulfate (1.5 mol) with pump P4 with flow rate 5.7 ml/min. Residence loop 2 having residence time 5 min and temperature 40-50 ^oC. collect outlet of residence loop 2 in flask apply cooling, gradually add 141 g of water while maintaining the internal temperature at 15 ^oC. after 1 hr stirring oil layer was separated and removed, and aqueous layer was washed with toluene[10]. Water was added to this layer and distilled out benzaldehyde at atmospheric pressure. 50% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution was added in this at temperature below 20 ^oC. aqueous layer was transfer to flask and distilled under atmospheric pressure to obtained ethyl methyl amine.

Advanced Process Design.

in initial process we perform the reaction in two part. But in advanced process we can perform the reaction simultaneously as shown in fig. aq. Ethyl amine feed with pump A with the flowrate 4.78 ml/min and benzaldehyde feed with pump B having flowrate 5.22 ml/min.

after completing residence time of 1 min in residence loop 1 (10 ml). we provide a separator at the outlet of residence loop 1 which separate the aq. And organic layer and organic layer collected in flask C simultaneously feed with pump C having flowrate 5.3 ml/min in microreactor II (55 ml). Another side Dimethyl sulfate i.e solution D feed with Pump D with the flowrate 5.7 ml/min at the residence time 5 min. at the out late of microreactor we provide a water bath which cool the solution and collect in flask for further process.

Table 3. Comparison of batch process with continue process

Operate manner	Batch	Continuous flow
Yield (%)	87	93
Purity (%)	96 (diamine formation)	98
Reaction time	stirred for hours after completing the Addition of reagents	stage I: 1 min stage II: 5 min

Conclusion

In summery an expeditious and high yielding process for synthesis of Ethyl methyl amine from aqueous ethyl amine (70%) via a continuous flow reactor has been setup. Formation of diethyl methyl amine will be avoided by providing less residence time. The process is readily adapted for preparation of analogous compounds and can easily be scaled-up by increasing reactor size or operating several reactors with high throughput in parallel. The apparatus used to deliver the results for the large-scale experiments is still being used for further batches.

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